

Data Management Plan

Deliverable n. 1.5

Deliverable information	
WP	1 - Coordination and Management I
Document dissemination level	Public
Deliverable type	Document, report
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Contributors	CNR, CHANGES, 3DR
Date	31.01.2026
Document status	Finalised
Document version	V. 1
Due Date	M 6

Project information

Project start date: 1st October 2025

Project Duration: 48

Project website: <https://placemus-xr-eccch.eu/>

Project contacts

Project Coordinator: Eva Pietroni

CNR - ISPC

e-mail: eva.pietroni@cnr.it

WP Scientific coordinator: Eva Pietroni

CNR - ISPC

e-mail: eva.pietroni@cnr.it

Project Manager: Daniela Maria Palamà

CNR - ISPC

e-mail: danielamaria.palama@cnr.it

PlaceMUS XR consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Italy
2	CHANGES	Fondazione CHANGES- Cultural Heritage active Innovation for Sustainable Society	Italy
3	CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	France
4	UT	Université de Tours	France
5	MF	Mezzo Forte	France
6	OU	The Open University	UK
7	Hangvető	Hangvető Zenei Terjeszto Tarsulaskorlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag	Hungary
8	GEOFolkLife	GEORGIA Folk Life	Georgia
9	3DR	3D Research Srl	Italy
10	SD	S.D. Cinematografica	Italy
11	PK/CUT	Politechnika Krakowska	Poland
12	COBO	Comune di Bologna	Italy
23	BCM-BGIR	Ministero della Cultura	Italy
14	MdV	Museo del Violino	Italy

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCI	Creative Cultural Industries
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC CRM	Comité International pour la DOCumentation Conceptual Reference Mode
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science project
EITF	ECHOES Integration Task Force
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
HDTO	Heritage Digital Twin Ontology
HW	Hardware
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework
StaC	Stakeholders Council
SW	Software
TB	Terabyte
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work Package

This document was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

Executive summary

The Data Management Plan is a mandatory component of Horizon Europe projects and provides information about:

1. The project data summary
2. Guiding principles around data management
3. How to make project data FAIR
4. Data security, ethics and confidentiality.

Further to these basic requirements, this document drafts the expected integration roadmap with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) through the cooperation with the European Cloud for Heritage Open Science - ECHOES project (Grant Agreement n.101157364).

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
1	10/03/2026		Daniela Maria Palamà CNR- ISPC Matteo Greco – CNR ISPC Eva Pietroni– CNR ISPC
2	16/03/2026		Daniela Maria Palamà CNR- ISPC Matteo Greco CNR- ISPC Eva Pietroni CNR- ISPC Alberto Nico – CHANGES Marco Cozza – 3DR Romano Aloisi – 3DR

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PROJECT INFORMATION	1
<i>Project contacts</i>	1
PLACEMUS XR CONSORTIUM.....	2
ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
DOCUMENT HISTORY	4
INTRODUCTION	6
1. DATA MANAGEMENT WITHIN PLACEMUS XR – AN OVERVIEW	7
1.1 <i>Regulatory framework for PlaceMUS XR Data Management</i>	7
1.2 <i>Open science and Data Management</i>	8
1.3 <i>Integration with ECHOES and the ECCCH</i>	8
2. DATA SUMMARY	10
2.1 <i>Data Types and Sources</i>	11
2.2 <i>Estimated Data Volumes</i>	13
2.3 <i>Purpose of the Data</i>	13
2.4 <i>Target Groups</i>	13
3. FAIR DATA.....	15
3.1 <i>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</i>	15
3.2 <i>Making data accessible</i>	15
3.3 <i>Making data interoperable</i>	18
3.4 <i>Increase data re-use</i>	18
4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	18
5. DATA SECURITY	19
6. ETHICS	19
REFERENCES.....	21

Introduction

The PlaceMUS XR Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the procedures the project will implement for the handling of data during and after the end of the project, what kind of data will be collected and their size, and how the FAIR principles will be applied during and after the project implementation. The DMP is an iterative document reflecting the evolving needs and activities of the project and, further, the continuous interaction with the ECHOES project and its roadmap towards the integration in the ECCCH. This first version reflects the state of the art at the starting phase of the project activities where general principles and approaches are summarised. The plan will be updated to include additional measures taken by the project as a whole and necessary adjustments to align and integrate what here foreseen. Three further releases, namely D1.6 Mid-term version of DMP (M17), D2.3 Mid-term version of DMP (M36) and D2.4 Final version of DMP (M48) are envisaged in the GA.

To facilitate the drafting of the first version of the Data Management Plan, a survey (Figure 1 - DMP Survey) has been distributed among partners to collect the relevant information about the expected project data, their origin, type, size, according to the Work Packages of relevance.

1. WP	1.1 - Task	2. Tools (if relevant)	3. Itinerary (if relevant)	4. What is the content of the data generated by your WP? [1 row per data type]	4.1. If "other" in column C please specify	5. Is data created or reused?	5.1 If reused please specify provenance	6. Expected type of data	6.1. Please detail if proprietary/open source AND specify format	7. Is the use of AI tools envisaged?	7.1 Please specify	8. Expected data Size	9. Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	10. Retention	10.1. If "other" in column H please specify	11. Access to personal information	11.1. If "other" in column J please specify	12. Dissemination level	13. User licence	13.1 If Other, please specify
-------	------------	------------------------	----------------------------	--	--	-------------------------------	---	--------------------------	--	--------------------------------------	--------------------	-----------------------	--	---------------	---	------------------------------------	---	-------------------------	------------------	-------------------------------

Figure 1 - DMP Survey

1. Data management within PlaceMUS XR – An overview

1.1 Regulatory framework for PlaceMUS XR Data Management

The PlaceMUS XR DMP is based on the following regulations, which define its purpose and limitations as established by the EC and the Consortium as a whole. Further, the provisions of the GDPR relating to the processing of personal data are taken into account in the data management process.

Grant Agreement 101233325

- Article 13.1 - Sensitive information
- Article 14 - *Ethics*
- Article 15 - *Data Protection*
- Article 16 - *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) - Background and Results - Access Rights and Rights of Use*
- Article 17.1 *Communication – Dissemination - Promoting the action*
- Annex 5 - Specific Rules for Articles 13, 14, 16, 17

PlaceMUS XR Consortium Agreement

- Article 8 - Results
- Article 9 - Access Rights
- Article 10 - Non-disclosure of information
- Attachment 1 - Background included

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

1.2 Open science and Data Management

PlaceMUS XR will manage its data and metadata in line with the FAIR principles, ensuring that the data and metadata will be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

In line with the Common European data space for cultural heritage and ECCCH recommendations, PlaceMUS XR will adopt a Policy for Open Science, applied to all results obtained by the project partners where this is practically and legally possible.

As established in the GA, open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the project results will be ensured.

In particular, it will be ensured that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence or a licence with equivalent rights.
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries/authors will retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

1.3 Integration with ECHOES and the ECCCH

The **European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)** is a European Union initiative for the creation of a digital infrastructure that will connect cultural heritage institutions and professionals from a wide range of disciplines providing cutting-edge tools for digitising artefacts, studying artworks, and documenting data, with the aim of improving preservation, conservation and restoration procedures,

Data Management Plan

paving the way for transdisciplinary collaboration in the field of cultural heritage.¹ Under the umbrella of the ECCCH, the European Commission through Horizon Europe is funding, with a budget of around €110 million, a significant number of innovative projects that contribute to enrich the Cultural Heritage Cloud by developing tools and services to digitise, preserve and valorise Europe's cultural heritage.

The ECHOES project, whose mission is to develop and implement the ECCCH, operates within a multi-layered ecosystem of stakeholders. At the core of this ecosystem are the ECHOES consortium members and the broader network of ECCCH-funded sister projects, including PlaceMUS XR. Their close coordination aims to facilitate the integration of data, interactive tools and services developed by each project, through the adoption of common technical standards and interfaces that allow for interoperability and scalability across the European cloud environment², leaving in the hands of each project the integration of their outputs in the ECCCH. In D3.1 ECHOES Integration Strategy for datasets, *tools and workflows*, the ECHOES project derives three key pillars for its Integration Strategy³:

- To build a federated open-source infrastructure that enables the creation of practical applications driven by Cultural Heritage (CH) communities' needs for both tangible and intangible CH
- To integrate results of past, current and future ECCCH-related projects regarding data, services, digital processes and applications.
- To enable and foster innovative, collaborative co-creation of new knowledge around Digital Commons.

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en#key-events-and-milestones-related-to-the-ecch-initiative

² Kotzinos, D., Chambers, S., Barbot, L., Durco, M., & Dalla Torre, G. (2025). ECHOES Integration Strategy for datasets, tools and workflows with potential for reuse in ECHOES (D3.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751335>

³ Pollé, A., Vendrix, P., Czech, L., Petitcol, R., Gallini, C., Stadlinger, E., Steindl, C., Pühr, A., Marçal, E., Szatucsek, Z., Habibi Minelli, S., Nowak, A., EF, CNRS, FSP, ONB, PCSS/PSNC, & META. (2025). ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17599162>

The aim is the creation of a federated architecture, where heritage institutions retain full ownership and control over their data while participating in a shared, interoperable ecosystem. Each federate operates according to its own rules and technologies but participates in the larger system through standardized interfaces and shared protocols and data models.⁴

The ECHOES Governance has established two working groups aimed at tackling and facilitating the integration process, namely the ECHOES Integration Task Force (EITF), a dedicated task force composed of ECHOES Work Package Leaders and representatives from the ECCCH-related projects (including existing ECCCH-sister projects) and responsible for coordinating day-to-day integration activities across the ECHOES ecosystem, and the Stakeholders Council (StaC) composed of representatives from the other ECCCH-funded sister projects (including PlaceMUS XR) and European initiatives related to Cultural Heritage, whose activities are planned to start in March 2026.

2. Data Summary

Table 1 - Data Summary provides a synthetic overview of the current data portfolio of PlaceMUS XR, including total expected data volume, created/reused balance, repository planning, based on the current DMP inventory.

KPI	Value
Total datasets mapped	86
Overall expected maximum data volume	17.622 TB
Created data	73 datasets / 10.541 TB / 59.8% of total size
Reused data	13 datasets / 7.082 TB / 40.2% of total size
Distinct repositories mentioned	13
Largest data family by size	Raw acquisition data: 8.560 TB (48.6%)
Largest data family by number of datasets	Documentation & reports: 39 datasets (45.3%)

Table 1 - Data Summary

⁴ Sielli, A., Avgousti, A., Hermon, S., Demetrescu, E., Kowalska, J., Pawlikowski, K., Axaridou, A., Cignoni, P., Andújar, C., Durco, M., Kritsotakis, E., Theodoridou, M., Tzortzakakis, E., & Pitikakis, M. (2025). ECHOES Data Strategy for the CH Knowledge Base (D6.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751757>

Data Management Plan

The 13 repositories currently mentioned are: CNRS sDrive for PlaceMus XR project, DIGILAB, EC Funding & Tenders Portal, GitHub, GitLab, Harmony Space website, Microsoft® SharePoint / Teams, Music Computing Lab website, Project website, Publisher / DOI landing page, SD CINEMATOGRAFICA repository, YouTube, Zenodo.

2.1 Data Types and Sources

In PlaceMUS XR, data are produced and reused to populate the project itineraries and related digital contents, to enable the design and development of applications and services, and to support project management through the production of technical and administrative documentation. Additional outputs include guidelines and methodological resources intended to promote consistency, good practices, future reuse, and dissemination material (text, audio, and video). Statistical data are primarily generated through the project's experience analytics system (Analytic service) and through surveys, providing evidence for monitoring user expectations, needs, practices, interaction, evaluating engagement, and assessing the performance and impact of project activities and services. At the same time, the development of data models provides the semantic and structural framework required to describe, manage, and interconnect the project's information assets.

Family	Typical contents	Typical formats	Typical volume range (upper bound)	Total size (upper bound)
Media & XR assets	360° photos, 3D models (places/objects), spatial audio, multimedia packs for storytelling.	MP4, ProRes/DNxHR, DNG; JPG/PNG/TIFF; OBJ/PLY/LAS; glTF; 3D Tiles; WAV/ambisonics (where applicable).	~5GB up to multi-TB	3,76 TB
Raw acquisition data	Raw footage, 360° video recordings, point clouds,	MP4, ProRes/DNxHR, DNG; JPG/PNG/TIFF; OBJ/PLY/LAS; glTF; 3D Tiles; WAV/ambisonics	~5GB up to multi-TB	8,56 TB

Data Management Plan

Software & code	Open-source Web3D/XR tools, ATON.js framework, Unity/engine frameworks, web prototypes (HTML/CSS/JS), code + configuration.	Source code repositories; HTML/CSS/JS; Unity/engine project files; build artefacts; JSON configuration.	~100MB to ~5GB (occasionally larger when bundled with media)	0,041 TB
Semantic data & metadata	Knowledge base artefacts, metadata formalisms, experience ontology, semantic datasets.	RDF/TTL, JSON/CSV mapping tables; documentation.	~100MB to ~5GB	0,01 TB
Documentation & reports	Deliverables, milestones, guidelines, QA reports, statistics, PDFs, spreadsheets.	PDF, DOCX, XLS/CSV; diagrams.	~100MB to ~5GB	5,2 TB
Human-subjects / personal data	Interview-related materials and consent-driven registrations (where applicable); aggregated/anonymised results intended for publication.	PDF/DOCX summaries; raw responses stored securely where applicable.	~100MB (raw data may be larger depending on methods)	0,5 GB

Table 2 - Dataset families (high-level)

Data types (see Table 2 - Dataset families (high-level)) will be texts, images, maps and cartographies, videos, spoken audio, environmental sounds, spatial-acoustic data and immersive sound, recording of musical performances, interactive 3D models (mesh and point clouds), questionnaires, reports. Research outputs will be software and hardware interfaces (tools, platforms), applications, museum setup, and scientific papers. **Different levels of resolution and elaboration** of audio-visual contents will be generated, shared, preserved and enriched with metadata: i) RAW data, which can be useful to further elaborations starting from the original resources; and ii) elaborated and optimized data for online access.

Reused data come from a variety of sources, ranging from existing literature, archives, discography, the results of previous projects (funded at national and EU level), existing software and frameworks, and Open Street Map cartography. Also, the code of software/frameworks/services (ATON, MINERVA, AGAMI, SMBVT, GeoViz, etc.) will be reused and integrated for the implementation of more than a dozen tools which operate in a modular and interlinked manner to offer coherent

Data Management Plan

production pipeline for planning, creating and sharing scenarios at different scales of representation (see PlaceMUS XR GA).

All the different type of data will be used in a strict compliance with existing intellectual property rights or, in any case, in strict compliance with intellectual property law.

2.2 Estimated Data Volumes

The current estimated maximum volume of data to be generated or re-used within the project is approximately 17.6 TB. Of this, about 10.5 TB are expected to be newly generated and about 7.1 TB correspond to re-used data. The largest shares are represented by raw acquisition data (approximately 8.6 TB), documentation and reports (about 5.2 TB), and media and XR assets (about 3.8 TB), while software and code, semantic data and metadata, and human-subjects/personal data account for a comparatively limited volume. These figures should be considered as current maximum estimates and may be further refined during the project.

2.3 Purpose of the Data

The purpose of the data, both generated and reused, is to create advanced digital solutions that enhance visitors' engagement with cultural heritage and contextual information, while also improving access to musical experiences. It will introduce design and simulation tools to:

- develop, share, and reuse interactive content whose value, interpretability, and interactive potential are strengthened through virtual reality and digital technologies.
- analyse, design, and assess visitor interactions, supporting the work of museum curators, creative industries, students, and researchers.

2.4 Target Groups

Several target groups that could benefit from the PlaceMUS XR data and tools have been identified in the project proposal.

Museum professionals, as the PlaceMUS XR will support museum curators and exhibition designers in decision-making processes implementing methodologies aimed at (i) improving the accessibility of their resources; (ii) presenting their content in the most effective way to the public proposing solutions that can improve

interaction, personalization, emotional solicitation, accessibility and understanding of CH.

Creative Cultural Industries (CCIs) professionals in Cultural Heritage will benefit from the scalable and modular tools developed to create new experiences with places of music and storytelling, reducing their efforts and strengthening their competitiveness.

Educational institutions, as educators will be able to use prototypes to teach but also to co-create new scenarios with/for their students, re-using tools and contents. Students will be able to explore XR scenarios to increase their knowledge of music venues, being more engaged in-depth studies.

Musical academies/Conservatories Ensembles, as their active involvement will give visibility and prestige to educational institutions. In addition, young artists will be able to use the results of PlaceMUS XR to analyse and strengthen their awareness of the fundamental relationship between sound and space in musical practice.

Scientific communities and academics, as scholars will be able to use tools to enrich PlaceMUS XR scenarios with new places, itineraries, contents or to make analyses and comparisons among places and deepen their research in a multidisciplinary perspective.

Local communities will be facilitated in discovering the stories of their hometown's musical heritage and help in preserving its legacy, starting promotion or co-creation activities.

Tourists and general public as users of exhibit spaces, whose access to sonic heritage and place of music will be enhanced and facilitated as dataset and tools can be re-used in museums installations (holographic showcases, video-projections, immersive kiosks), where contents can be accessed online or downloaded.

Policy makers and financial actors, given the current absence of the category of "historical soundscapes" in the known experiences of cultural tours, and who could choose to invest in extending the project with new implementations and in cultural tourism strategies.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

This section explains how PlaceMUS XR will make its data and research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The focus in this first release of the deliverable is on setting project-wide rules (identifiers, metadata, repositories, licensing, and provenance). These rules will be refined as concrete datasets are produced and deposited.

Dataset naming follows a consistent internal identifier scheme (defined by a common prefix [DSPX] followed by a four digit [progressive number]) linked to WP/Task ownership. For published datasets and software releases, persistent identifiers (typically DOIs or PID in general) will be defined by the chosen trusted repositories. A DOI will be associated to the project results labelled as “public”, being dataset, deliverables or prototypes published in Zenodo. They will be accessible also via the PlaceMUS XR and the ECHOES projects web portals so that the maximum accessibility and dissemination will be ensured. A minimum metadata set will be applied across outputs (title, creators/affiliations, dates, location/coverage where relevant, methods, rights/licence, funding, and relations to publications/software, where available).

Rich metadata will be provided to facilitate discovery and potential re-use of project outputs. Metadata will cover the main descriptive, technical, administrative, and rights-related elements needed to identify, understand, and contextualise the data, including identifiers, relations to other outputs, and subject keywords. Widely adopted general standards such as Dublin Core, complemented by domain-relevant schemas or controlled vocabularies whenever appropriate. Keywords will be included to improve search and discovery, and metadata will be made available in machine-readable form through the chosen repositories and services, so as to support harvesting and indexing.

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository

Data will be deposited, whenever possible, in trusted repositories appropriate to the type of output following the principle '*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*'.

Data Management Plan

The project foresees the use of DIGILAB-IT, Zenodo, and Git-based software repositories as the main environments for accessible and citable outputs, while some working data or very large files may also be managed through institutional or project cloud services, as detailed in Table 3 - PlaceMUS XR Repositories

. Where supported by the repository, outputs will be assigned persistent identifiers that resolve to the digital object, notably in DIGILAB-IT, Zenodo, and software publication workflows; this is generally not ensured in other cloud-based storage environments. Repository choice will depend on the nature, size, sensitivity, and intended reuse of the data.

Where open access cannot be provided (e.g., rights limitations, personal data, or extremely large raw acquisition packages), the project will publish at least the associated metadata and, where feasible, derived/curated subsets suitable for reuse.

Repository	datasets	total max (GB)
CNRS sDrive for PlaceMUS XR project	6	106,1
DIGILAB-IT	15	7611,1
EC Funding & Tenders Portal	22	1063
GitHub	7	35
GitLab	1	50
Harmony Space website	1	0,1
Microsoft SharePoint / Teams	28	6777,3
Music Computing Lab website	1	0,1
Project website	7	1060,2
Publisher / DOI landing page	1	5
SD CINEMATOGRAFICA	2	3000
YouTube	2	10
Zenodo	31	1228,2

Table 3 - PlaceMUS XR Repositories

Data

Where data are openly shared, they will be made accessible through free and standard access mechanisms provided by the selected repositories and platform services, including web-based access over standard protocols and metadata exposure through OAI-PMH, where available, for harvesting and indexing. Where restrictions apply, access will be provided upon request in accordance with the

Data Management Plan

project's access policies and the conditions defined for the specific resource, both during and, where relevant, after the end of the project. In such cases, access will be granted through the platform's authentication and authorization system, which will be used to verify the identity and access rights of the requester.

Some contents could be protected by intellectual property rights (for example copyright) and cannot be publicly available, as in the in case of pre-existing resources coming from archives or discography, the use of which may be granted for the PlaceMUS XR case studies implementation only, but with limitations or constraints for successive sharing and re-use. Similarly, data of sensitive nature will not be accessible. In the case partners would have constraints due to pre-existing commercial agreements of HW and SW tools or dataset, **at least metadata and appropriate methodological documentation** will be released on the ECCCH, and **data access guidelines/conditions** will be provided. Tools protected by the secret of invention are not included in the project. Anyway, almost all existing tools and framework proposed in the project **are already open source** and they will be enriched by new functions. A derived open-source version can be obtained for tools which at present are not open.

Personal or sensitive data will not be open access and any document envisaging their use will be anonymised before publication.

Metadata:

Following both the GA and the ECHOES Integration Strategy⁵ and in line with the FAIR principles, metadata will be openly available under a CC0 licence and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s) and embargo); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, their organisations and the grant. If relevant, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

⁵ ECHOES Project 101157364 – Deliverable 3.1 ECHOES Integration Strategy for datasets, tools and workflows

3.3 Making data interoperable

Interoperability will build on open formats, controlled vocabularies and semantic modelling practices that support exchange and reuse across disciplines. In particular, the project is considering the ECHOES Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO) as the main semantic backbone for information representation; the current HDTO documentation is a first draft aligned with CIDOC CRM 7 and related models and is intended to support integration and extensibility. Community-endorsed CIDOC CRM mapping and RDF (Resource Description Framework) implementation practices will be followed where applicable, while additional project-specific models for experience-related information will be developed and progressively aligned through mappings and qualified links to related resources. As this work is still under development, a more detailed interoperability strategy will be provided in future updates of this DMP.

3.4 Increase data re-use

Reuse will be enabled through standard licensing, interoperable formats, rich documentation, and explicit provenance links between source data and derived outputs. The documentation provided with datasets will include, where relevant (for instance in case of digitisations and virtual reconstructions) methodological and processing notes, software/version information, definitions, and other contextual elements needed to validate analyses and facilitate reuse. Data will be made as openly available as possible and licensed, where applicable, through standard reuse licences in line with the Grant Agreement; the current inventory includes licences such as CC BY, CC BY-NC, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, CC BY-NC-ND, GPL v3, and GPL v3 combined with third-party licence conditions for some software components. Project data and related outputs will remain reusable by third parties after the end of the project according to the applicable licences and access conditions. Provenance and quality assurance will be documented through metadata, workflow and version information, validation procedures, review processes, and integrity checks appropriate to each dataset family.

4. Allocation of resources

The Project Coordinator will primarily be in charge of the data management and of ensuring that the project data and meta-data is compliant with the FAIR Principles.

Data Management Plan

Each project partner is responsible and will cover the direct and indirect costs related to the storage, archiving, re-use and security of data in institutional repositories. Some repositories do not envisage costs for their use (i.e. Zenodo, GitHub, GitLab). PlaceMUS XR project budget has been dedicated to cover the costs of personnel that will be dedicated to supporting the process of integration and alignment with ECHOES.

5. Data security

Data security will primarily rely on the safeguards and preservation measures provided by the selected trusted repositories and institutional storage environments. These are expected to support secure storage, backup and recovery procedures, controlled transfer mechanisms, and, where relevant, access control for restricted resources. Data intended for long-term preservation and curation will be deposited in trusted repositories, while sensitive data will not be published in identifiable form and will be anonymised before any dissemination. A more detailed strategy for long-term preservation, curation responsibilities, and repository-specific security measures will be further refined in future versions of this DMP, also building on the policies and services of the repositories selected for the project.

6. Ethics

Ethics issues will be thoroughly discussed in a dedicated deliverable, namely D1.7 Ethics and Gender Equality issues, due at M6 and that will have a second, updated version with D1.8 Final version of EGEP at M17. The project will comply with Article 14.1 of the GA, ensuring that the action will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

The PlaceMUS XR results have an exclusive focus on civil applications and do not envisage dual use potential risks, as they have no applications in the military sector nor have the potential to create negative consequences for health and safety, agriculture, the environment or national/international security.

Data Management Plan

Artificial Intelligence (AI) will be used to facilitate multilanguage translation, text to speech, automatic/semi-automatic text optimization for different audience and age groups, included children of different age groups and teenagers. It is also envisaged in Task 4.2 “*Accessibility-oriented AI*” whose activities will investigate and apply AI algorithms to improve accessibility of text and audio contents through automated or semi-automated procedures, as multilanguage translation including Braille, text optimization and formal adaptations. Text to Speech and virtual avatars in Sign Language will be experimented. AI could be used also to produce some graphic content to represent ideas and abstract concepts, or to evoke historical events. In any case, its use will be declared in the metadata and in the resources released to the public.

WP5 and WP6 envisage a set of surveys, both preliminary ones, targeting the participants of the PlaceMUS XR consortium, museums curators, CCIs, scholars, educators, students, and general public, and verification ones to test tools, scenarios, and the overall experience in terms of interactions, usability, accessibility, usefulness, and pleasantness, and improve criticalities. Users’ participation in surveys is voluntary. Participants will sign informed consent forms detailing the research purpose, methods, risks, and benefits, data use and storage. Personal data of interviewees will be used exclusively for statistical and research purposes pertaining to the PlaceMUS XR project and will in all cases be anonymised. Data will be reviewed for consistency and inaccuracies will be corrected or removed; participants may request corrections. No personal data will be transferred to external organizations. Personal data will be securely stored on GDPR compliant servers, accessible only to authorized personnel and they will be deleted after a period of 6 months from the end of the project. They will not be migrated to ECCCH.

Photos and videos will be used to create contents, dissemination material, on the project web page and social media posts and, sometimes, in deliverables. Informed consent (see the example in Annex I) will be obtained by asking the individuals concerned to sign a specific form which will require not only authorisation to use their image, but also the scope of authorization, the purpose of the research activity, terms and conditions (duration, geographic scope, compensation, rights, withdrawal, privacy).

References

ALLEA (2023) The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023. Berlin. DOI [10.26356/ECOC](https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

Grant Agreement 101233325 Project: 101233325 — PlaceMUS XR — HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01 Associated with document Ref. Ares (2025)6451440 - 07/08/2025

PlaceMUS XR Consortium Agreement

Cignoni, P., Siotto, E., Potenziani, M., & National Research Council. (2025). ECHOES Ethics and Data Management Plan (D1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17513615>

Pollé, A., Vendrix, P., Czech, L., Petitcol, R., Gallini, C., Stadlinger, E., Steindl, C., Pühr, A., Marçal, E., Szatucsek, Z., Habibi Minelli, S., & Nowak, A. (2025). ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17599162>

Kotzinos, D., Chambers, S., Barbot, L., Durco, M., & Dalla Torre, G. (2025). ECHOES Integration Strategy for datasets, tools and workflows with potential for reuse in ECHOES (D3.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751335>

Sielli, A., Avgousti, A., Hermon, S., Demetrescu, E., Kowalska, J., Pawlikowski, K., Axaridou, A., Cignoni, P., Andújar, C., Durco, M., Kritsotakis, E., Theodoridou, M., Tzortzakakis, E., & Pitikakis, M. (2025). ECHOES Data Strategy for the CH Knowledge Base (D6.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751757>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Report on a European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage – Ex – ante impact assessment*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/64014>

D1.5

Data Management Plan

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *European collaborative cloud for cultural heritage*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/83783>

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/social-sciences-and-humanities/cultural-heritage-and-cultural-and-creative-industries-ccis/cultural-heritage-cloud_en#key-events-and-milestones-related-to-the-ecch-initiative

<https://cidoc-crm.org/Resources/heritage-digital-twin-ontology-echoes>

<https://www.fairsfair.eu/recommendations-practice-support-fair-data-principles>

Image and video release form

PlaceMUS XR Project - Kick-off Meeting

Location: Museo del Violino, Cremona, Italy

Date: November 18-19, 2025

CONSENT FOR USE OF IMAGE AND VIDEO MATERIALS

I, the undersigned, hereby grant permission to the PlaceMUS XR Project and its partners to use photographs, video recordings, and any other visual materials in which I appear, taken during the kick-off meeting held at the Museo del Violino in Cremona on November 18-19, 2025.

SCOPE OF AUTHORIZATION

I authorize the use of such images and videos for all communication purposes related to the PlaceMUS XR Project, including but not limited to:

- Official project websites
- Social media channels
- Press releases and media communications
- Publications (both digital and print)
- Presentations and promotional materials
- Reports and documentation for funding agencies
- Scientific publications and conference presentations
- Educational and dissemination activities

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

1. **Duration:** This authorization is valid for the entire duration of the PlaceMUS XR Project and for archival purposes thereafter, without time limitations.
2. **Geographic scope:** The authorization is valid worldwide without territorial restrictions.
3. **Compensation:** I waive any right to compensation for the use of my image and likeness in the materials described above.
4. **Rights:** I understand that the materials may be edited, modified, or adapted as necessary for the purposes stated above, provided that such editing does not alter the meaning and intended message of the original audio-visual content. The materials will be sent to the concerned parties for approval before publication.
5. **Revocation:** I understand that this consent cannot be revoked once the materials have been published or distributed.
6. **Privacy:** I acknowledge that I have been informed about the processing of my personal data in accordance with applicable data protection regulations (GDPR - Regulation EU 2016/679).

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from HORIZON-CL2-2024-
HERITAGE-ECCCH-01-04, under Grant Agreement n. 101233325